

SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PLANS, STAKEHOLDERS' PARTICIPATION, AND STATUS OF ITS MATERIALIZATION: BASIS FOR POLICY BRIEF

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ABSTRACT

In the United States, school improvement plans become the basis of the programs and activities for the next year. In the Philippines, DepEd schools are mandated to create and prepare a three-year plan, the School Improvement Plan (SIP). This study determined the level of SIP and stakeholders' participation, and the status of its materialization in Banga east district, South Cotabato. Descriptive and correlational research designs was used among 56 School-Based Planning Team of schools as respondents. Findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between the SIP implementation level and the stakeholders' participation in the partnership program, and in the status of materialization of SIP. It implies that if the SIPs are well crafted and implemented, stakeholders will participate actively in partnership program resulting to a better materialization of SIPs. Recommendation includes the review of DepEd Order no.44, s2015 which is the basis of SIPs in public schools nationwide. Schools should create innovations to increase stakeholders' participation in terms of furniture and learners' school supplies and uniforms. Policy on mandating schools to have Memorandum of Understanding with stakeholders before the start of each year. Additionally, schools must create initiatives and programs to improve enrolment and feeding program.

Keywords: *School improvement plans, partnership program, materialization, Banga east, stakeholders*

INTRODUCTION

Schools worldwide have unique needs and challenges in delivering quality and inclusive education. To operate properly, each school must have a plan, which can serve as the framework or development. In the Philippines, DepEd schools are mandated to create and prepare a three-year plan, the School Improvement Plan (SIP). Based on DepEd Order no.44, (2015), SIP has three phases: Assess, Plan, and Act. It also contains the current year's Annual Implementation Plan (AIP). In DepEd South Cotabato, schools follow this mandate to follow the SIP and involve stakeholders' participation in partnership program (Division Memorandum SGOD no. 35, 2020).

The School-Based Planning Team (SPT) plays a big part in the materialization of SIP (Abalario, 2022). The problem lies where stakeholders and citizens are just participants during the implementation of SIPs. In its press release DepEd (2025), emphasized the urgent needs of classrooms and facilities in schools nationwide which can be addressed through partnership programs. To address the issue of the engagement and partnership of the stakeholders in the school improvement plans, this research was conducted to determine the level of school improvement plans, determine the level of participation of stakeholders in partnership programs, and assess the status of the materialization of SIP. This research aimed to contribute support to the improvement of educational policy and practice by shedding light on creating SIPs that reflect each school's specific needs and the facilitation of strong, long-lasting partnerships between stakeholders.

This evolving paradigm reflects an increased emphasis on stakeholders' demand for active involvement and engagement from policymakers, necessitating a shift in how policy is formulated (Paraiso, 2022). The SIP, a comprehensive plan spanning three school years, emphasizes the significance of community and stakeholder support. It empowers stakeholders to actively participate in the planning, execution, monitoring, and evaluation of school improvement initiatives, aligning resources and interventions with specific needs.

Gross et al. (2015) found that inclusive school councils positively impact student outcomes. Scholarly research has emphasized the importance of multiple-stakeholder engagement in effective school management. As former DepEd Secretary of Education Luistro articulated in 2015, the SIP concept has flourished further through community partnerships.

While existing research has scrutinized various facets of educational policies and programs, the majority has centered on initiatives such as the Brigada Eskwela program. In addition, studies have investigated stakeholder participation in the SIP, focusing primarily on implementation effectiveness (Guzman, 2022), implementation scope and practices (Nicdao, 2020), and stakeholder participation. Moreover, the implementation of SIP needs the involvement of the stakeholders, where, in the different localities of the regions, their involvement could be stronger and firmer (Paraiso, 2022). The researcher is trying to address the gap in the study.

To address the issue of the engagement and partnership of the stakeholders in the school improvement plans, this research was conducted to determine the level of implementation of school improvement plans, determine the level of stakeholders' participation in partnership programs, and assess the status of materialization of SIPs. This research aims to contribute support to the improvement of educational policy and practice by shedding light on the implementation of SIPs in each school and the facilitation of strong, long-lasting partnerships between stakeholders, which play a vital role in the status of the materialization of SIPs. The study could also be the basis of their policy enhancement for improving and developing schools.

Research Questions

The study determined the level of implementation of school improvement plans, assessed the level of stakeholders' participation in partnership programs, and assessed the status of materialization of SIPs in public elementary schools in the Banga East district. answered the following:

1. What is the level of implementation of school improvement plans in the following phases:
 - 1.1 assess;
 - 1.2 plan; and,
 - 1.3 act?
2. What is the level of stakeholders' participation in partnership programs in terms of:
 - 2.1 infrastructure;
 - 2.2 technology and appliances;
 - 2.3 furniture;
 - 2.4 wellness, health, and nutrition;
 - 2.5 learners' school supplies; and
 - 2.6 teaching and non-teaching personnel support?
3. What is the status of the materialization of SIP in terms of:
 - 3.1 school profile;
 - 3.2 access; and
 - 3.3 quality?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the implementation of school improvement plans and the participation of stakeholders in partnership programs?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of school improvement plans and the status of materialization of SIP?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of stakeholders' participation in the partnership program and the status of SIP materialization?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized descriptive and correlational research designs. Quantitative approach was used to determine the level of implementation of school improvement, the level of stakeholders' participation in the partnership, and the status of the materialization of SIP. The scope of this study encompassed a comprehensive examination of implementation of the school improvement plan, stakeholders' participation SIP materialization in from 2022-2024.

The research was carried out to eight elementary schools of Banga East district, situated within the Schools Division of South Cotabato, Philippines. The study employed a total enumeration where 7 SPT members of 8 schools become the respondents. Waterfall data gathering procedure was carried out in strict accordance with academic and ethical standards.

The study's data collection instruments consist of three sets of survey questionnaires meticulously crafted to collect the necessary data for comprehensive analysis. Pilot testing was conducted before the questionnaire was employed to the respondents with Cronbach's alpha of 0.469. A 5-point Likert scale was used with highest numerical rating of 5 and lowest rating of 1 was used in the study. Mean was used to determine the level of implementation of SIP, level of stakeholders' participation, and status of SIP materialization. The Pearson correlation was used to measure if there is a significant relationship between the level of implementation of school improvement plans and stakeholders' level of participation in the partnership program, a significant relationship between the level of implementation of school improvement plans and the status materialization of SIP, and significant relationship between the level of stakeholders' participation and the status of materialization of SIP (Turney, 2023).

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary of the Level Implementation of School Improvement Plans in terms of Assets, Plan, and Act.

Indicators	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Assess	4.42	Very High Level	Most of the programs and activities in the phase was properly implemented.
Plan	4.41	Very High Level	Most of the programs and activities in the phase was properly implemented.
Act	4.28	Very High Level	Most of the programs and activities in the phase was properly implemented.
Grand Mean	4.37	Very High Level	Most of the programs and activities in the SIP were properly implemented.

Table 2. Summary of Participation of Stakeholders in Partnership Program

Indicators	Mean	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
Infrastructures	4.22	Very High Level	Stakeholders are deeply engaged, actively contributing to the provision and acquisition of school needs.
Technology and Appliances	4.24	Very High Level	Stakeholders are deeply engaged, actively contributing to the provision and acquisition of school needs.
Furniture	4.11	High Level	Stakeholders are actively involved and contributing to the provision and acquisition of school needs.
Wellness, Health, & Nutrition	4.16	High Level	Stakeholders are actively involved and contributing to the provision and acquisition of school needs.
Learners' School Supplies and uniform	4.11	High Level	Stakeholders are actively involved and contributing to the provision and acquisition of school needs.
Teaching and Non-Teaching Personnel Support	4.21	Very High Level	Stakeholders are deeply engaged, actively contributing to the provision and acquisition of school needs.
Grand Mean	4.18	High Level	Stakeholders are actively involved and contributing to the provision and acquisition of school needs.

Table 3. Summary of the Status of Materialization of SIP

Categories of SIP	Mean	Description	Interpretation
1. School Profile	4.30	Fully Materialized	Most programs and activities have been completed, and the intended outcomes have been achieved.
2. Access	4.33	Fully Materialized	Most programs and activities have been completed, and the intended outcomes have been achieved.
3. Quality	4.41	Fully Materialized	Most programs and activities have been completed, and the intended outcomes have been achieved.
Grand Mean	4.35	Fully Materialized	Most Programs and activities have been completed, and the intended outcomes have been achieved.

Table 4. Relationship between the Level of Implementation of SIP and the Level of Participation of Stakeholders in the Partnership Program

Pair of Variables	n	r	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Implementation of School Improvement Plans Vs Level of Stakeholders' Participation in the Partnership Program	56	0.80	<0.0001	Very Strong Relationship

**At 0.05 level of significance

Table 5. Relationship Between the Level of Implementation of School Improvement Plans and Status of Materialization of SIP.

Pair of Variables	N	r	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Implementation of School Improvement Plans Vs Status of Materialization	56	0.44	0.007	Moderate Relationship

**At 0.05 level of significance

Table 6. Relationship Between Level of Stakeholders in Partnership Program and the Status of the Materialization of SIP.

Pair of Variables	n	R	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Stakeholders' Participation in the Partnership Program Vs Status of Materialization	56	0.42	0.001	Moderate Relationship

**At 0.05 level of significance

DISCUSSION

Table 1 summarizes the level of SIP in the phases of Assess, Plan, and Act. Assess has a mean of 4.42 and is described as being at a very high level of implementation. This means that the assessment phase was properly implemented. Act has a mean of 4.28 and is also at a very high level of implementation. This means that the act phase was properly implemented. The result implies that the elementary schools in Banga East district have implemented their SIPs properly. It results from careful planning, strong leadership, and active engagement of stakeholders, like in the implementation of Brigada Eskwela (Solidarios, 2022). With this level of implementation, the real challenge is how to maintain this level. School administrators must be able to adapt to the different needs of the school every time. In three years, schools must prepare

their AIPs to prepare for the incoming year. According to DepEd Order No. 44 (2015), the AIP is very important in DepEd schools since it is the basis for how the MOOE must be used. Thus, the AIPs should be planned properly, or the school's expenditures will not match its needs.

Table 2 summarizes the level of stakeholder participation in the partnership program. Technology and appliances have the highest mean of 4.24, which indicates a very high level of involvement. Furniture and learners' school supplies and uniform have the lowest mean of 4.11, which indicates a high involvement level. With a grand mean of 4.18, stakeholders' participation in the partnership program is only high level. The result means that the stakeholders in elementary schools in Banga East district are actively involved and contributing to the provision and acquisition of school needs. This implies room for improvement regarding stakeholders' participation in the partnership program. It is necessary to create a stakeholder engagement plan to improve stakeholders' participation and ensure stakeholders' engagement in schools in a year (Lyle, 2024). There are many ways to enhance stakeholders' involvement. The best way is to make them a part of every program and activities. In DepEd schools, stakeholders are mandated to be part of decision-making in schools as part of SBM (DepEd, 2024). Stakeholders become more participative when they feel they are co-owners of school decisions.

Table 3 shows that quality has the highest mean of 4.41, indicating that programs and activities under access have been completed and the intended outcomes have been achieved. It also means that schools have fully materialized their activities This is one of the bases to be evaluated as a SBM level 3 school (DepEd Order no. 44, 2015). The school profile has the lowest mean of 4.30, indicating that the SIP fully materialized in the Banga East district.

With a grand mean of 4.35, the SIPs in elementary schools in the Banga East district were fully materialized. The result means schools could complete most of their program and activities based on their SIPs. SIPs should be simple and direct in finding ways to focus on PIAs. SIPs should always consider the welfare of the learners (Coker, 2022). The result implies that the materialization status of SIP for the years 2022-2024 was fully materialized in elementary schools of Banga East District. Feeding programs is a challenging aspect in school profiles. During feedings programs, some recipients are absent and was no able to receive their allocation of food and supplies. According to Ordinario (2016), feeding programs are unsuccessful in other schools due to a lack of proper documentation, thus affecting school profiles. This includes photos of food, recipients, and attendance of the recipients.

Table 4 shows that the relationship between the implementation of school improvement plans and the level of stakeholders' participation in the partnership program is represented by a correlation coefficient (r). The strength of the relationship is $r = 0.80$, which has a p -value of <0.0001 , which is too small compared to $\alpha = 0.05$ (Turney, 2023). There is enough evidence to claim that computed $r = 0.80$ is significantly different from zero (0). The result implies that the level of implementation of school improvement plans

and the level of stakeholders' participation in the partnership program have a very strong relationship. Additionally, the results reveal that intensifying improvement plans suggests a greater possibility of increasing stakeholders' participation (Escobar, 2019). This means that if the SIP were fully crafted, stakeholders would fully understand what will happen in three years and know their role in all school activities and programs (Sedmak, 2023). With the following results, alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Table 5 shows that the relationship between the level of implementation of school improvement plans and the status of SIP materialization is represented by a correlation coefficient (r). The strength of the relationship is $r = 0.44$ and has a p -value of 0.007, which is too small compared to $\alpha = 0.05$ (McLeod, 2023). There is enough evidence to claim that computed $r = 0.44$ is significantly different from zero (0). The result implies that the level of implementation of school improvement plans and the status of materialization of SIP have a positive and moderate relationship. Goals do not materialize; a good strategy is always needed (Francia, 2020). The result means that if school improvement plans were crafted properly, SIP was materialized. Additionally, the results reveal that giving high intensity to school improvement plans suggests a greater possibility of an increase in SIP materializations in schools in Banga East District. With the following results, the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Table 6 shows the relationship between the level of stakeholders' participation in the partnership program and the status of SIP materialization is represented by the correlation coefficient (r). Their strength of relationship is 0.42 and has a p -value of 0.001, which is small compared to $\alpha = 0.05$ (McLeod, 2023). There is enough evidence to claim that computed $r = 0.42$ is significantly different from zero (0). The result implies that stakeholders' participation in partnership programs has a positive and moderate relationship. According to Guzman (2022), the higher the stakeholders' involvement in the partnership program, the higher the status of SIP materialization will also increase. With the following results, alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings, the following conclusion was drawn:

School improvement plans in the assessment, plan, and act phases are carefully crafted and implemented. Regarding stakeholders' participation in the partnership program, the study found out that there is a high level of participation among the stakeholders. That almost all programs and activities related to school profile, access, and quality were fully materialized in the schools. There is a significant relationship between the SIP implementation level and the stakeholders' participation in the partnership program, and in the status of materialization of SIP. It is also found out, that there is a significant relationship between the level of stakeholders' participation in the partnership program and the status of the materialization of SIP.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Act has the lowest mean among the phases of School Improvement Plans. Thus, it is highly recommended that the Department of Education and the schools will focus more on the act phase policy enhancing of the SIP which may clearly show how programs and activities can be implemented in schools.
2. The level of stakeholders' participation in terms of furniture and learners' school supplies and uniform has the lowest mean. Both schools need high participation and involvement but still need improvements. Thus, it is recommended that schools and administrators will make innovations and partnership strategies to improve stakeholders' participation in the acquisition of furniture and learner's school supplies.
3. The mean for stakeholders' participation in partnership programs is high. To ensure partnerships with different stakeholders reach a very high level, it is recommended that schools enhance partnership programs through MOUs.
4. The school profile has the lowest mean among the factors in materializing SIPs. Thus, it is recommended that schools focus on issues related to the decrease in enrolment. Schools may also focus on the feeding program and explain why the number of children wasted in schools has not become zero despite the continuous feeding program.
5. Future researchers may study on the innovation of partnerships with different new stakeholders and their participation in schools' improvements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers, declares that this research is in compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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